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Research Article

Development and Characterization of Neem and Sandalwood based Herbal Face Wash Tablets

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to formulate and evaluate of herbal Face wash tablets using Neem and Sandalwood powder. Cosmetic are used to cleanse the skin, beautify it and improve the look. Cosmetic formulations that include natural substances particularly herbs have become highly effective in meeting the different requirements of different skin types. Herbs have been used to achieve healthy and beautiful skin since ancient history, demonstrating their function in the cleanliness and attractiveness aspects of the cosmetic industry. These tablets include active ingredients such as cleansers, exfoliators, and moisturizers that dissolve on contact with water to create a lather that effectively removes dirt, oil, and impurities from the skin. Their compact and lightweight design makes these face wash tablets perfect for travel, providing a convenient, mess-free substitute for large liquid containers. The Neem plant is mentioned in the literature due to its antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties. Moreover, over a period of time the therapeutic and cosmetic benefits of Sandalwood have also been well established. Six formulations were prepared and were evaluated for various functional properties like color, appearance, consistency, foaming pH 1, fragrance, and spread ability.

INTRODUCTION

The term "cosmetic" is derived from the Greek word "kosmetikos," which signifies adornment and preparation. Sometimes called body art, it is one of the oldest known forms of human ritual.

Cosmetics are substance or product used to enhance or alter the appearance of the face, as well as to improve the fragrance and texture of the body. Most cosmetics are formulated for application on the face and body. They typically consist of either synthetic or natural ingredients, or

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a combination of both¹. Herbal cosmetics, often categorized as natural cosmetics, refer to herbal formulations intended for external application on areas such as nails, skin, and hair. These products serve multiple purposes, including coloring, covering, softening, cleansing, nourishing, styling, and altering appearance. Herbal cosmetics have gained significant popularity due to their composition, which consists entirely of herbs and plants, and their lack of adverse effects on the human body. These natural remedies provide essential nutrients and beneficial minerals to the skin, leading to an increasing demand for organic and herbal beauty products. This trend presents new opportunities for manufacturers to innovate and create products that align with consumer preferences.^{2,5} A variety of herbs are utilized in skincare formulations, including Neem, Turmeric, Liquorice, Sandalwood, Aloe vera, etc. A facial cleanser or face wash is a product that maintains skin cleanliness, eliminates germs, and promotes a smooth and fresh appearance. It also hydrates the stratum corneum without inducing irritation, contributing to a youthful and vibrant look. Facial cleansers can be utilized for various purposes, including cleansing, reducing wrinkles, combating acne, moisturizing, and enhancing skin fairness.⁹¹¹ Face wash tablets represent a formulation that combines the components of face washes into a tablet format. These tablets are designed to reduce costs, decrease packaging size, and limit the use of harmful preservatives, while also being conveniently portable. Face wash tablet is intended for single use, providing an adequate amount to prevent excessive application.^{3,6,7} In the present study, herbal face wash tablets containing Neem and sandalwood powder have been developed. Sandalwood (*Santalum album*) belongs to the Santalaceae family and is recognized for its health-promoting properties, primarily due to its high concentration of bioactive compounds. This species is noted for its

therapeutic potential, which can be attributed to the presence of essential oils and other beneficial constituents such as santalol, santalene, and other sesquiterpenes. The various parts of the sandalwood tree exhibit antimicrobial properties by inhibiting the growth of pathogens and disrupting their cellular structures. Additionally, sandalwood demonstrates anti-inflammatory effects by modulating the activity of pro-inflammatory enzymes, including cyclooxygenase (COX) and lipoxygenase (LOX). Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), belonging to the Meliaceae family, is recognized for its health-promoting properties, primarily due to its high antioxidant content. The therapeutic potential of *Azadirachta indica* is attributed to its abundance of antioxidants and other beneficial active compounds, including azadirachtin, nimbolinin, nimbin, nimbidin, nimbidol, salannin, and quercetin. Additionally, various parts of the neem plant exhibit antimicrobial properties by inhibiting microbial growth and disrupting cell wall integrity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Herbs and Chemicals

Herbs

All the herbs (Neem and Sandalwood powder) were collected from local market.

Chemicals

Acacia powder-Binder, Sodium lauryl sulphate-Surfactant, Crospovidone-Disintegrant, Magnesium stearate -Lubricant, of laboratory grade were used in the study.

Method of Preparation of Face Wash Tablet

1. Weigh 10% of Neem and Sandalwood powder from a total tablet weight of 500 mg.

2. Accurately weigh Sodium Lauryl Sulfate (SLS), Crospovidone, Acacia, and Magnesium stearate in specified proportions, and then triturate these mixture using a mortar and pestle.
3. Weigh 500 mg of the triturated mixture for use in tablet compression.
4. Direct compression technique is employed to form tablets, where the powder blend of ingredients is compressed directly into a die cavity, resulting in a solid compact.
5. Fine tablets are obtained by adjusting the lower die level and modifying the concentrations of SLS, Acacia and Crospovidone.
6. Finally collect the tablets.

Preformulation Studies

Bulk Density:

Bulk density refers to the apparent density of a powder when subjected to specific conditions. It represents the volume of the uncompressed powder and is measured in grams per cubic centimeter (g/cm³).

Bulk density = weight of sample in gram/volume occupied by the sample

Tapped Density:

Tapped density refers to the apparent density of a powder measured under standardized conditions. It represents the volume of powder after it has been subjected to mechanical tapping. The tapped density of a powder is calculated using the formula: Tapped density = weight of sample in grams / Tapped Volume

Hausner's Ratio and Compressibility Index:

Hausner's ratio and compressibility index serve as indicators for predicting the flow characteristics of particles in a straightforward manner. Both metrics

are derived from bulk density and tapped density measurements.

Hausner's Ratio:

Hausner's ratio is a numerical value that is significant in industrial applications for assessing the flow ability of powders. A ratio exceeding 1.25 indicates poor flow ability. It is calculated using the formula:

Hausner's ratio = Tapped density (g/cm³) / Bulk density (g/cm³)

Compressibility Index:

The compressibility index quantifies the propensity of a powder to be compressed, reflecting its ability to settle and engage in interparticle interactions. This index is represented by Carr's index (%), which is calculated as follows:

Carr's index (%) = (Bulk density - Tapped density) / Tapped density * 100

Angle of Repose:

The angle of repose is the angle that distinguishes the transitions between different phases of granular materials and is commonly utilized to assess interparticle interactions. It is determined using the formula:

Tan θ = h / r

Where: h = Height of the pile, r = Radius of the base of the pile, θ = Angle of repose.

Formulation Table:

Table 1: Formulation Table

Ingredients (%)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Neem Powder	10	10	10	10	10	10

Sandalwood Powder	10	10	10	10	10	10
SLS	25	30	35	25	30	35
Acacia	20	10	15	15	20	10
Crospovidone	30	35	25	35	25	30
Mg. Stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5

Fig.1. Herbal Faces Wash Tablets.

Evaluation Of Face Washes Tablets:

Physical Evaluation:

The physical characteristics of the formulated face wash tablets were assessed based on parameters such as color and overall appearance.³

Wash ability:

To evaluate the wash ability of the face wash tablet, the formulation was applied to the skin and subsequently rinsed with water, followed by a manual inspection.³

pH:

The pH of the face wash tablet was adjusted to align with the skin's natural pH to prevent irritation. This was achieved by preparing a 1% aqueous solution of the formulation, which was then, measured using a calibrated digital pH meter at a constant temperature.⁶

Foam ability via Cylinder Shake Method:

Fifty milliliters of water were placed in a 250ml cylinder, into which the tablet was dropped. The cylinder was then covered with a hand and shaken vigorously for several minutes. The volume of foam generated was subsequently measured.⁷

Weight Variation:

For the weight variation assessment, twenty tablets from each formulation were individually weighed using an electronic balance. The average weight was calculated, and deviations were noted in comparison to this average. The acceptable weight variation limit should not exceed ± 7.50 .
Formula:

$$\% \text{ Weight Variation} = (\text{Individual Weight} - \text{Average Weight}) / \text{Average Weight} * 100$$

Hardness Test:

The hardness of the tablets was determined using a Pfizer hardness tester, which measures the tablet's ability to withstand mechanical shock. Hardness is expressed in Kg/cm². A random selection of 3-5 tablets from each batch was tested, and the results were recorded. The average hardness value for the tablets ranged from 3 to 5.

Friability Test:

A friabilator was employed to assess the friability of the tablets. The device was activated, and the tablets were weighed. The count was adjusted to 100 by pressing the count key, and the test was conducted by similarly adjusting the time. The tablets were then placed in the friabilator for evaluation.⁸

Thickness:

The Thickness of the tablets is measured with the help of Vernier caliper. Thickness of the tablet should be in limit of ± 5 Kg/cm².⁸

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Pre-Formulation Studies

Formulation	Angle of repose	Hausner's ratio	Carr's index (%)	Flow properties
F1	44	1.37	25.3	Poor
F2	41	1.28	22.4	Passable
F3	37	1.24	20.3	Fair
F4	39	1.27	25.2	Passable
F5	35	1.21	19.3	Fair
F6	32	1.13	16.5	Good

Table 3: Comparative Evaluation Results of Trial Formulations

Formulation	Colour	Hardness Test (kg/cm ²)	Thickness Test (mm)	Friability Test (%)	Weight variation (mg)	pH	Wash ability
F1	white	4.0	4.5	0.92	495	6.1	Bad
F2	white	4.1	4.5	0.87	503	6.1	Bad
F3	white	4.3	4.5	0.82	502	6.1	Good
F4	white	4.0	4.5	0.78	504	6.1	Good
F5	white	3.9	4.5	0.70	498	6.1	Good
F6	white	4.2	4.5	0.62	500	6.1	Excellent

Fig.2. Foam Formed in Face Wash Tablet Formulation

Table 4: Foaming properties of formulations

Formulation	Properties of foam
F1	Small amount foam production
F2	No foam
F3	Small amount foam production
F4	Small amount of foam production
F5	Good foam production
F6	Excellent foam production

The main purpose of developing a face wash tablet to consumer's convenience subsequent cost effectiveness and made the face wash available to the general public. A brief review of literature was conducted to understand the product and patent status of Neem and Sandalwood its medicinal effect and availability in current marketplace. Experimentation was conducted by developing tableting technology for face wash that offered great convenience of tablet face wash for consumers while travelling or for short-usage period face wash and waste reduction. After concluding various comparative studies of the drug and their excipient with evaluations of face wash, the formulated batch (F6) produced an excellent foaming effect with a fine face wash.

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CONCLUSION

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